

Comparison of OOP positions to external catalogs for selected plates.

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We have extracted from COMPASS (OATo copy) the positions of all observations in ten 7x7 degree regions centered at 9 declinations (approx: -80,-60,-40,-20,0,20,40,60,80) and RAs corresponding to POSSII/SERCII centers. These objects were then matched to various external catalogs (2MASS, SDSS3, UCAC, NPM, SPM,FIRST) and position difference statistics found. Here we discuss the results of the 2MASS and SDSS3 comparison, unless otherwise noted you can assume the other catalogs gave comparable results. This dataset then consists of approximately 70 full plates per survey in the north (extra ones at 0 and 80 degrees) and 50 full plates in the south and over 300 and 200 partial plates in the two hemispheres respectively. So for example for 2MASS and the XP plates the total number of observations compared (after 3 sigma clipping) was over 14 million on 391 partial plates and on the XS over 12 million on 265 partial plates.

Obviously with this kind of dataset we can do quite alot. What we have concentrated on are three things:

- 1) Correlations with mean differences per plate and declination.
- 2) Examination of residual maps as a function of magnitude.
- 3) Affirmation of a global magnitude function in the mean differences.

For all points I will bring the discussion with the 2MASS match of XP using partial or full plates then compare this to the other surveys and finally with the other comparison catalogs.

There are a number of known shortfalls with these comparisons i.e.:

- 1) we use all objects, it would be cleaner to use just stars
- 2) the proper motions in the comparison catalog have not been utilized
- 3) SDSS5 exists
- 4) The XE and S surveys are a combination of PIM and VIM files which confuses some of the interpretation we are trying to do.

Many of these shortfalls are being dealt with, however I feel the results will be quite robust to any changes. If you feel something very important has been missed please let me know, but minor changes will have to be put on the todo list - everything can be done but takes time and if I don't want this comparison to take me to a pension a priority has to be set.

I apologise in advance for the number of graphs. I tried to be selective but soon learnt in discussions with people here that saying things did not (or did) change was not sufficient people needed to see for themselves. I will put all (literally 100s) of the graphs that have gone into this report on the web (<http://www.to.astro.it/smart/GSC/plateresids/>) so if you do not believe me when I make a statement of the form 'results for other surveys/comparison catalogs/plates were the same/different' you can go there and see for your self.

1 Correlations with mean differences per plate and declination.

For each full plate the mean difference was calculated. As the areas chosen were centered on second epoch positions so very few of the first epoch plates were completely covered, to still have some results the criteria for considering the plate 'full' was that there was at least 25 square degrees covered. In figure 1 each point is the mean differences of the XP and 2MASS position along with it's error for a number of full plates plotted against the plate declination. The solid line shows the mean of these mean differences and the dotted lines the standard deviations, if the flow of the points differs from this line there is a correlation between declination and mean difference. In this case, fig. 1, there appears to be no correlation.

The figures 2 to 9 are the same plots for the various surveys as indicated in the titles. The northern II epoch surveys (XP,XJ,XI figures 1 to 3) have no evident correlation between the declination and the mean difference. The southern II epoch surveys (XS,IS figures 7 and 8) appear however to have a slight correlation however the magnitude is certainly smaller than the sigma of the means and the two trends are not consistent. The first epoch northern plates (N,XE,XO figures 4 to 6) as said before are on different grids hence the plates often not 'full' and also the proper motions will have a much larger effect hence the larger noise. Finally the lone southern first epoch survey (S figure 9) which does have the same centers as the second epoch so therefore 'full' plates, does show some evidence of correlations similar to the IS however again more noise probably due to proper motions and hence again a trend that is smaller than the noise of the means. While the first

Table 1: Mean systematic errors as function of survey.

Survey	RA''	Dec''
XP	0.10+/-0.06	0.01+/-0.07
XJ	0.10+/-0.06	-.02+/-0.04
XI	0.09+/-0.05	0.01+/-0.05
N	0.07+/-0.10	0.03+/-0.09
XE	0.18+/-0.21	0.21+/-0.14
XO	0.18+/-0.21	0.21+/-0.14
XS	-.15+/-0.06	0.09+/-0.08
IS	-.15+/-0.10	0.11+/-0.07
S	-.03+/-0.15	-.04+/-0.15

epoch values have question marks, both because of the differing centers in the north and the proper motion effects in both hemispheres, from table 1 we can see that the mean difference between I and II epochs are different as would be expected from the systematic errors found in the derived proper motions.

2 Examination of residual maps in function of magnitudes.

In figure 10 we produce the histogram of the residuals for two plates (A2XL = XP565 and A2F3 = XP127). These are approximately equal density plates (46K and 50K matches in 2MASS) at different declinations. The first thing to note is that the mean RA differences, $0.13''$ and $0.15''$ shown in the boxed legend are significantly different from zero and significantly different between themselves. This implies that to remove the mean offsets the plates should be treated separately.

In figure 11 we produce the residual map for all objects matched in the respective plates. Note that while the overall structures are similar the details vary quite a bit. This indicates that applying a global mask will still leave residual systematic errors.

In figures 12 to 16 we produce the residual maps for the objects in different magnitude bins. As you can see the mean differences tend to grow from the lower magnitudes close to the Tycho reference catalog to the plate limit, however the patterns tend to be similar. A complaint about the comparison in figure 11 was that the differences between the two plates may have been because of a different magnitude distribution, because of differing plate limits or backgrounds, however, comparing the two graphs in figure 15 which are for the same magnitude range again the overall structures are more similar but the differences are still evident. While from these the figures shown up to now it would seem that treating plates separately is preferable the actual reality will be also a function of the reference catalog and procedures used and a definitive answer will have to be found from an in-depth analysis of global and local reduction procedures.

Two final notes: These two plates were chosen at random, there exists plates with larger differences and also plates with smaller differences. The comparisons of SDSS3 and UCAC observations give very similar results for both plates.

From section 1 we note that the mean differences are independent of the declination. Hence we can combine all the plates to produce super masks as functions of survey. Also partially supported by the above comparison we can assume that partial plates can be used to improve the statistics of the subsequent masks. In figure 17 we plot the overall histogram for all XP comparisons and the mask for all magnitude ranges. In figures 18 through 20 we plot the same data binned in magnitude ranges. The XI and XJ surveys had very similar properties. The XO, XE and N surveys had very different properties and in figures 21 to 22 four comparison graphs are presented for the XO plates. The southern surveys are also quite different and in the figures 23 to 24 we reproduce the same 4 comparison graphs for the XS survey. These results come as no surprise they are included only for completeness sake. The SDSS3 and UCAC comparisons also produced consistent results.

3 Affirmation of a global magnitude function in the mean differences.

As indicated in the last section there does seem to be a consistent magnitude trend and to test this plots of mean magnitude vs difference were made. We compared objects from full plates and at all declinations for the different surveys. We could probably have used also partial plates as the distribution of magnitude ranges with respect to the plate position should be uncorrelated however the vignetting may cause a systematic that it was deemed better to avoid. We also split the samples into those objects within 9000 pixels of the plate center (approximately 2.5 degrees, this is for VIM plates for the PIM the value was 5300 pixels) and outside this radius to see if the magnitude term is global.

In figure 25 we produce the magnitude function for the XP plates. There is a clear positive correlation that is zero around the magnitude of the reference frame (Tycho2 10-11) and then monotonically increases up to 19th where the number of pixels is low hence the centroiding is essentially magnitude independent. The lack of a clear break between saturated and unsaturated objects maybe due to the fact that we are looking at many plates hence the saturation point varies or maybe something inherent in the centroiding process that we do not understand (for example perhaps the centroids are dominated by the wings hence saturation plays a much smaller role than we thought). The fact that the three samples internal, external and all objects have the same form implies that for these plates there is no dependence on plate position.

Figures 26 thru 33 show the same plots for the surveys XJ,XI,N,XE,XO,XS,IS and S. A few comments:

- 1) Most of the forms are different which may be considered a combination of the different pixel properties and saturations.
- 2) The XE and S show a hint of a splitting of the function in the three zones, however these survey are a combination of PIM and VIM files and no matter how hard I tried it was very difficult to combine the results from different scales. In fact using the incorrect radius tends to mimics the effect we are looking for so I would not put too much weight here until a more careful analysis is carried out.
- 3) The XS southern plates show slight splitting of the magnitude function dependant on plate position. The statistical noise in these graphs after 12th magnitude is negligible so this has to be something physical, combinations of bad polar alignment and bad guiding could produce this effect, or something that we have not thought of. Deciding if this means we cannot assume a global magnitude function for these plates will be a consideration that needs to combine both the proposed reduction techniques and their noise and comparing that to the size of this systematic effect.

4 Summary of results.

4.1 Correlations with mean differences for complete plates and declination.

While there may be trends of the order of $.05''$ in the mean differences with declination the overall picture is that the systematic errors are declination independent. The differing systematic errors between the I and II epochs are consistent in sign with the proper motion systematics found in previous work. We have tested to see if the magnitude of these differences are consistent with the observed proper motion systematics.

4.2 Examination of residual maps in function of magnitudes.

The residual maps show increased amplitudes as you get further from the reference catalog but the patterns do not change as functions of magnitude. Two example plates from the same survey showed significant small scale differences in the mask pattern, sufficient I would say for an attempt to do single plate mask modeling rather than global mask modeling. The residual maps from different surveys are, as expected, quite different.

4.3 Affirmation of a global magnitude function in the mean differences.

There is an evident global magnitude function that would be easily calibrated. For some of the surveys this function may have a different form for the internal and external parts of the plates but these represent the extremes and while a final decision requires a full consideration with the new reduction procedures it will probably be the case that these differences can be ignored. The exact reason for this magnitude function are still unclear especially since there does not seem to be a relation to the saturation or a survey wide function.

These tests provide a good starting point for development of a new reduction procedure. Now the tests are in place it will be easy to re-run them when we have new results which provide a powerful tool for the evaluation of any new procedures.

Figure 1: Declination vs mean systematic differences per XP plate compared to 2MASS in arcseconds. Top in RAcos(dec) and bottom in Dec. The error bars on each point represent the error of the mean. The solid lines, and values in the legend, are the mean of all mean differences and the dotted lines represent the sigmas of the solid lines. The title reports the number of plates compared.

Figure 2: As figure 1 for the survey XJ.

Figure 3: As figure 1 for the survey XI.

Figure 4: As figure 1 for the survey N (quick V).

Figure 5: As figure 1 for the survey XE.

Figure 6: As figure 1 for the survey XO.

Figure 7: As figure 1 for the survey XS.

Figure 8: As figure 1 for the survey IS.

Figure 9: As figure 1 for the survey S (first epoch SERC).

Figure 10: Histograms of the residuals between 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates. The numbers in the title indicate the mean RA and Dec in degrees while in the unboxed legend the mean ranges of RA in Hrs and Dec in degrees. The boxed legend indicates the mean and sigma of the difference in RA (multiplied by $\cos(\text{dec})$) and in Declination both in arcseconds before and after 3 sigma clipping. In the x axis title the line styles are explained and the total number of comparisons after 3 sigma clipping.

Figure 11: Residual maps for all objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates. The X and Y axis represent the pixel positions of the objects on the plate. In the Y title we report the number of bins in the Y axis, the number of objects/bin, and the declination mean and standard deviation before and after 3 sigma clipping. In the X axis we report the number of bins in the X axis, the total number of objects in the comparison, the RA mean and standard deviation before and after 3 sigma clipping and finally the actual number of objects used in the calculation of the residual arrows (e.g. after 3 sigma clipping in each bin and dropping bins without sufficient comparisons). The arrow in the top left is represents 1'' and the box size is shown in the middle under the title.

Figure 12: Residual maps for objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates in the magnitude range 11-13. Labels and scale are as described in figure 11.

Figure 13: Residual maps for objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates in the magnitude range 13-15. Labels and scale are as described in figure 11.

Figure 14: Residual maps for objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates in the magnitude range 15-17. Labels and scale are as described in figure 11.

Figure 15: Residual maps for objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates in the magnitude range 17-19. Labels and scale are as described in figure 11.

Figure 16: Residual maps for objects in common between the 2MASS and the positions from the A2XL and A2F3 plates in the magnitude range 17-19. Labels and scale are as described in figure 11.

Figure 17: Top graph: Residual histograms for all objects in common between 2MASS and the XP positions. The 14 million objects appear on 391 partial plates and have the mean and sigmas reported in the boxed legend. Bottom graph: Global mask for all common objects regardless of magnitude, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 18: Residual maps for 2MASS/XP comparison in the magnitude range 11-13 and 13-15, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 19: Residual maps for 2MASS/XP comparison in the magnitude range 15-17 and 17-19, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 20: Residual maps for 2MASS/XP comparison in the magnitude range 19-21, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 21: Top graph: Residual histograms for all objects in common between 2MASS and the XO positions. The 5 million objects appear on 259 partial plates and have the mean and sigmas reported in the boxed legend. Bottom graph: Global mask for all common objects regardless of magnitude, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 22: Residual maps for 2MASS/XO comparison in the magnitude ranges 13-15 and 17-19 shown for comparison to the XP graphs, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 23: Top graph: Residual histograms for all objects in common between 2MASS and the XS positions. Bottom graph: Global mask for all common objects regardless of magnitude, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 24: Residual maps for 2MASS/XS comparison in the magnitude ranges 13-15 and 17-19 shown for comparison to the XP graphs, titles as in figure 11.

Figure 25: Magnitude vs mean systematic differences for all objects on full XP plates compared to 2MASS in arcseconds. The three lines represent selection of objects inside a 9000 pixel radius, outside that radius and all plate. The numbers along the bottom represent the number of objects (in thousands) in these three areas that were used to calculate the respective point, they are offset only to aid reading.

Figure 26: As figure 25 for the survey XJ.

Figure 27: As figure 25 for the survey XI.

Figure 28: As figure 25 for the survey N (quick V).

Figure 29: As figure 25 for the survey XE.

Figure 30: As figure 25 for the survey XO.

Figure 31: As figure 25 for the survey XS.

Figure 32: As figure 25 for the survey IS.

Figure 33: As figure 25 for the survey S (first epoch SERC).